

Assessment of Architects Adoption of Green Smart Design Strategies in High-Rise Office Building in Lagos Nigeria

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Abstract. With 200 million people, Nigeria has limited access to adequate urban infrastructure and power supply. The global threat of urban explosions and climate change has compelled developed cities to prioritize renewable energy and CO₂ emission reduction. This research aimed to investigate architects' adoption of GSB design strategies in view to improve energy usage in high-rise office buildings. The objectives are to identify the different GSB design strategies available, the architect's knowledge, and the extent of their adoption in practice. A review of relevant literature with a simple descriptive statistical survey was conducted with 174 structured questionnaires using a Likert scale ranking. 143 of these were returned for analysis using the SPSS statistical tool. The results revealed that GSB is at a developing stage due to a lack of adequate architect participation. There is general knowledge of GSB design strategies and their major benefits, but there is a low level of adoption in practice due to inadequate training and programs. Passive energy design should be encouraged among professionals while prioritizing affordable eco-friendly materials that will help to optimize energy consumption in high-rise office buildings. Professional groups and the government should make people aware of GSB. GB certification of Nigeria should be set up to help more new and existing buildings get certified.

Keywords: Green Smart Building; Design; Adoption; Architects; Energy

1 Introduction

Human daily activities for survival exacerbate environmental negative impacts. [1] Climate change is caused by the use of fossil fuels, which emit greenhouse gases and increase the earth's temperature by 1°C. [2] The construction sector is known for excessive energy use, waste, environmental pollution, and degradation. [3] The global urban population explosion is disconcerting, as African cities are projected to have 61.8% of the 3.95 billion world population in cities. With over 200 million people, Nigeria has limited access to adequate urban infrastructure and power supply, forcing people to buy portable generators. Buildings at a global level utilize about 40% of

energy, 25% of water, and 40% of resources, and emit about 33% of greenhouse gases. These threats have compelled developed cities to prioritize sustainable building development.[5] To achieve this, environmentalists introduced 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) to deal with energy, CO₂, and other environmental problems in cities by separating economic growth from climate change, poverty, and inequality. [6] Furthermore, SDG goals 3, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 15, and 17 were identified as the benefits of G.B features in designs. [7] These encouraged the integration of the life cycle into green methods in practice. [8] In design planning, three sustainable objectives such as earth, people, and supply chain profits must be adopted.[9] Green building (GB), also known as sustainable building, uses building structures and environmentally resource-efficient processes throughout a building's life cycle, from planning to design, construction, operation, maintenance, and renovation. [8] and calls for cooperation among the construction team and the client [10] which helps traditional building design goals of cost, service, life cycle, and users' comfort. [11] Green smart buildings (GSB) promote technological optimization in GB. [7] list several GSB design strategies, including site potential and energy; building space and material use; improved indoor environmental quality; operational maintenance; waste reduction; recycling; sustainable design; active sustainable design; and smart technologies.[12] Nigerian cities are growing rapidly due to urbanization and lack revolutionary tools to improve the construction industry [13],[14],[15], and effort should be taken to explore solar energy services so that developers can operate low-cost intelligent buildings. [16] The architecture industry consumes a lot of energy and releases waste, making it an environmentally unfriendly industry. [17] According to [18], nearly two and a half times as much energy is used per square meter of floor space in high-rise office buildings with 20 stories or more than in low-rise buildings with 6 stories or less. The amount of energy used in high-rise buildings has gone up from 38% to 61% of the total amount of energy used in commercial buildings. [19] Nigeria's per capita energy consumption is 120.5 kWh, which is more than 10 times below the global average. [20] The study focused mainly on architects' practice because architects' detailed designs are needed before other professional designs. In addition, Lagos, which is the study area, is a megacity with about 14.86 million people in 2021. [4] Also known as the most economically viable state [21] with a total output of 136 billion dollars, accounts for more than a third of Nigeria's GDP [22], and would have been the fifth-largest economy in Africa if it were a country. [23] It has a greater concentration of architects than any other state, with about 60% of the country's commercial construction projects.[24] Lagos is home to the headquarters of most of the biggest architectural practices regulated by ARCON. [25] Thus, the study is important because of gaps identified in the literature on sustainable buildings such as cost, awareness, and adoption of GSB; skills; unavailability of power supply; security, and the need for Nigeria to catch up with technological innovations and sustainable development around the world. [26] GSB implementation must be done right from the pre-design to post-construction stages by an architect who is licensed in the art and science of building design and construction. [27],[28] The study aimed to investigate architects' adoption of GSB design strategies in Lagos to improve energy efficiency in the design of high-rise offices. The objectives are to identify different GSB design strategies available; assess the knowledge of architects on GSB, and examine architects' adoption of GSB design strategies in architects' practice in Lagos.

2 Literature review

Commercial buildings consume more than 60% of total energy consumption. Therefore, architects need to strategize on the best practices to resolve these issues right from the design stage. The study identified different GSB design strategies available, assessed the knowledge of architects on GSB, and examined architects' adoption of GSB design strategies in architects' practice in Lagos.

2.1 GSB design strategies

According to [29], GSB is a new-generation building incorporating BIM, GIS, Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and other technologies in GB. It saves resources and improves energy utilization while reducing environmental pollution and resource waste in the country. GSB helps to achieve maximum efficiency in the construction industry. It promises a better living environment and supports one of the sustainability principles by making the building less harmful to the environment.[26]. As shown in table 1, [7] identifies various GSB design strategies: optimized site potential; optimized energy; optimized building space; and material use; enhanced indoor environmental quality; optimized operational and maintenance practices; waste reduction and recycling; and passive sustainable design, active sustainable design, and smart technology). [12] According to [30], the site should have good building orientation and adequate building cost and performance. Materials such as insulated roofs and walls have significant effects on the indoor users' indoor comfort. [31][32] In addition, thermal comfort is achieved through the use of a double façade compared to a single façade on indoor air quality considering proper wall to window ratio, bright external wall painting, and the use of daylighting control devices, which reduce energy usage. [33] Building envelopes reduce air leaks in design; energy-saving devices and LEED-certified lighting aid energy usage in building operations. [34] According to [35], the life cycle of a building is dependent on proper operation and maintenance right from the design stage till post-occupancy. The value of GB became significantly high over time, which yielded more than ten times the return on investment, leading to increased property value and reduced maintenance costs. [36] Ultra-low flush toilets and low-flow showerheads result in improved water conservation. [37] The waste in landfills in construction and building operations should be reduced by providing waste collection bins, while liquid waste from the building can be recycled as greywater to generate electricity. [38] Passive energy-saving technology and proactive energy-saving adoption result in increased public perception of GSB awareness. Other alternative sources of energy include wind energy, inverters, biomass, and biogas.[39] Furthermore, in the [17] study, GB's use of advanced technology through IoT helps to achieve an effective design. Smart technologies include automatic doors, door face recognition systems, IP cloud home systems, wireless communication devices, and environmental monitoring control. Environmental monitoring control includes smart LED lighting; automatic temperature control; smart A.C; smart switches; gas leakage sensors; and health management, which includes body status sensors and homing devices. Entertainment sharing devices include mobile media and digital interaction sharing.

2.2 Knowledge and Adoption of GSB in Architect's practice

Architects' knowledge (awareness) of GSB, cost, skills gap in the implementation, epileptic power supply, and enabling policies have been identified as major limitations to the adoption of GSB.[26] GSB promotes technological optimization, well-being, comfort, improved energy use, and eco-friendly materials. The government at all levels should initiate enabling policies and opportunities.[40],[41],[42],[43] The implications for not adopting GB are continual conventional construction with maximal exploitation and resource depletion. Artificial Intelligent and GB features used in designs help to promote GSB. [44], [45], [46], [47] Factors that promote GSB design strategies in Taiwan have been identified as timers for extractor fans, multi-split AC, automatic photovoltaic solar panels, and automatic indoor air control systems. Green structures and green facilities were the focus of GSB design; green structures include roof insulation, exterior wall insulation, roof overhangs, concrete floor, large windows, low emission glass, sunroof, green roof, and adequate ventilation designs and shading devices. Some of the green features are light designs that use less energy, photovoltaic or solar power panels, rainwater storage, and coatings with low levels of volatile organic compounds.[12] [48] emphasized the need for an architect to strategize on an effective approach to design by considering the environment, economy, and social rights in practice. The materials the architects specify in the design proposals are all derived from the physical environment, and the manipulation of the design space may affect the local ecology. However, with the low adoption level, if Nigeria is in a global survival race, a new approach to architectural practice has to be adopted. Furthermore, the government should create enabling conditions and policies that allow stakeholders to construct more green buildings in Nigeria. In design, the consideration of solar power or photovoltaic systems and ventilation, double-paned glass, low emissive glass, natural resources, and the geographical environment should be encouraged right from the design stage or phases during the execution of green buildings. [49] [50] According to [27], architects consider factors such as security, structure, and facilities; lighting, ventilation, interior, and exterior space planning, and natural resources in design.

3 Methodology

This study investigates architects' adoption of GSB design strategies in high-rise office buildings in Lagos. Mixed-method research was adopted where secondary data was collected via a review of relevant literature, which helped to get adequate information for the structured questionnaire on GSB design strategies and energy consumption in high-rise buildings, architect knowledge of GSB, and its adoption in practice. The questionnaire was administered to the architects in Lagos because Lagos is a megacity known as the most economically viable state and known as the nation's largest urban area [21], also identified as the most populous city and commercial capital in the country. [23] In addition, Lagos has a greater concentration of architects than any other state in Nigeria, having most of the headquarters of the biggest architectural practices regulated by the ARCON, and having over 60% of the country's construction projects. [25] All these are important to ensure adequate and accurate views of the respondents

when investigating architects' adoption of GSB design strategies in high-rise office buildings in Lagos. According to [52], the population of architects in practice in Lagos is 1470 in 2021. The Raosoft sample size calculator adopted a confidence level of 95%, a margin of error of 7%, and a population proportion of 50%, which resulted in a sample size of one hundred and seventy-four (174). The first section was designed to collect brief respondents' information, while the second section gathered information on the existing GSB design strategies by adopting mixed questions with a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 being very significant, 4 being significant, 3 being average, 2 being low, and 1 being very low. The third and fourth sections were designed to gather data on the knowledge of architects on GSB and the extent of GSB adoption in architects' practice. They adopted mixed questions with a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 being very significant, 4 being significant, 3 being average, 2 being low, and 1. One hundred and seventy-four architects participated in the study. 147 out of the 174 questionnaires sent out were collected and returned for analysis, which is an 82.2% response rate and is believed adequate for the study. A simple descriptive frequency analysis was adopted using IBM SPSS statistics 26 for the analysis, while the results of the data analysis were presented with relatable works of literature.

4 Results and Discussions

4.1 Characteristics of respondents that participated in the study

This section gives respondents information that examines variables such as educational qualification, architect's ARCON registration, and work experience. 17 respondents (11.9%) were technicians; 22 respondents (15.4%) were technologists; 35 respondents (24.5%) were provisional 1, 42 respondents (29.4%) were provisional 2, and 27 respondents (18.9%) were fully registered architects. 16 respondents (11.2%) have an OND, 14 respondents (9.8%) have an HND, 26 respondents (18.2%) have a B.Sc., 83 respondents (58%) have an M.Sc., and 4 respondents (28%) have a Ph.D. 31 respondents (21.7%) had less than 5 years of experience, 60 respondents (42%) were between 5-10 years, 33 respondents (23.1%) were between 11-15 years, 16 respondents (11.2%) were between 15-20 years, and 3 respondents (2.1%) were between 20 years and above. The results show that all the respondents were educated, while the majority were undergoing tutelage under the supervision of a fully registered member. Thus, they have some level of experience, which is the basis for knowledge of GSB in practice.

4.2 Green smart building (GSB) design strategies

This section addresses research objective one. Variables such as the different GSB design strategies and GSB energy-efficient features were examined. 97 respondents (67.8%) agree with the life cycle assessment as a GSB strategy. An on-site and structural design efficiency strategy was chosen by 79% of respondents. Energy efficiency was chosen by 130 of the respondents. Water efficiency was chosen by 115 of the respondents, and materials by 117 of the respondents were chosen by 81% of the

respondents. 117 respondents (81.8%) agreed on indoor environmental quality enhancement as a GSB strategy, and 100 respondents (69.9%) agreed on operation and maintenance as a GSB strategy. 113 respondents (79%) agree on waste reduction as a GSB strategy; 106 respondents (74.1%) agree on passive sustainable design as a GSB strategy; 115 respondents (80.4%) agree on active sustainable design, and 118 respondents (82.5%) agree on smart technology as a GSB strategy. 89 respondents (62.2%) agree that the adequate wall-to-window ratio will provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 92 respondents (64.3%) agree that the heat reduction glass will provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 73 respondents (51%) agree that the energy-saving meters will provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 99 respondents (69.2%) agree that the external shading devices will provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 77 respondents (53.8%) agree that the LEED lights will provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 79 respondents (55.2%) agree that the automatic lights will provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 93 respondents (65%) show that the solar panel will provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 85 respondents (59.4%) agree that the automatic water closet will provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 91 respondents (63.6%) agree that the automatic door will provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 94 respondents (65.7%) indicated that the automatic gate would provide an energy-efficient feature in the design. 93 people (65%) stated that the automatic fire alarm system would be an energy-saving feature in the design. This result shows that respondents are familiar with GSB Design strategies and their components.

4.3 Knowledge of the architect on GSB

This section addresses research objective 2, variables such as GB definition, GB participation, GB efficiency, green products, GB environmental benefit, green building economic benefit, and green building social and health benefit. 3 respondents (2.1%) indicated that GSB is a building painted green; 73 respondents (51%) stated that GSB is a modern building; 77 respondents (53.8%) show that GSB keeps the environment's air clean; 82 respondents (57.3%) show that GSB improves health and social life, and 71 respondents (49.7%) indicated that GSB reduces maintenance costs. 11 respondents (7.7%) said they have been involved in GSB, 63 respondents (44.1%) said they have never been involved in GSB design, and 69 respondents (48.3%) indicated that they have never participated in GSB. 5 respondents (3.5%) strongly disagree that green products help to optimize energy; 4 respondents (2.8%) disagree that green products help to optimize energy, and 9 respondents (6.3%) were undecided on whether or not green products help to optimize energy. 83 respondents (58%) agree that green products help optimize energy use, and 42 respondents (29.4%) strongly agree that green products help optimize energy use. 2 respondents (2.1%) strongly disagreed that eco-friendly materials help to optimize energy. 98 respondents (68.5%) indicated the environmental benefits of GSB reduce water consumption. 86 respondents (60.1%) showed that the environmental benefits of GSB help to lower energy consumption, and 87 respondents (60.8%) said that the environmental benefits of GSB increase biodiversity. 74 respondents (51.7%) agree that the environmental benefits of GSB

include reducing greenhouse emissions. 116 respondents (81.1%) agree that the economic benefits of GSB are increased property values and occupancy rates, and 101 respondents (70.6%) agree that the economic benefits of GSB are job creation. 103 respondents (72%) agree that the economic benefit of GSB boosts human social performance; 100 respondents (69.9%) indicate that the economic benefit of GSB improves people's health and well-being, and 100 respondents (69.9%) agree that GSB increases property values and occupancy rates. The result shows the architect's participation is low, although they have vast knowledge of GSB and its benefits to users.

4.4 Adoption of GSB Design Strategies in Practice

This section addresses research objective 3 where variables such as GSB pre-design strategies adoption in practice, GSB design, and construction stage strategies adoption in practice 15 respondents (10.5%) strongly disagreed that GSB is only for new designs; 82 respondents (57.3%) disagreed that GSB is only for new designs; 12 respondents (8.4%) were undecided that GSB is only for new designs; 31 respondents (21.7%) agreed that GSB is only for new designs, and 3 respondents (2.1%) strongly agreed that GSB is only for new designs. 15 respondents (10.5%) are not sure whether GSB strategies can be used in all building types. 87 respondents (60.8%) agreed that GSB strategies could be used in all building types, and 41 respondents (28.7%) disagreed that they could be used in all building types. 133 respondents (93%) agree that GSB design strategies are adopted in practice at the pre-design stage; 121 respondents (84.6%) agree that GSB design strategies are adopted in practice at the design stage; 71 respondents (49.7%) agree that GSB design strategies are adopted in practice at the construction stage, and 62 respondents (43.4%) agree that GSB design strategies are adopted in practice at the post-construction stage. 131 respondents (91.6%) agree that site selection and planning should be used in GSB design. 89 respondents (62.2%) agree that building form/envelope and orientation should be used in GSB design. 107 respondents (74.8%) agree that energy-efficient materials should be used in GSB design. 91 respondents (63.6%) agree that space allocation for renewable roof solar control should be used in GSB design. 31 respondents (21.7%) agree that a wall-to-window ratio should be used in GSB design. 55 respondents (38.5%) agree that solar heating mechanisms should be used in GSB design, and 125 respondents (87.4%) agree that well-designed landscapes should be considered in GSB design and construction stage strategies. The wall-to-window ratio should be considered in GSB design and construction stage strategies. 58 respondents (40.6%) agree that double-skin façades should be considered in GSB design and construction stage strategies. 102 respondents (71.3%) agree that façade shading devices should be considered in GSB design and construction stage strategies. 52 respondents (36.4%) agree that façades in vibrant colors should be considered in GSB design and construction stage strategies. 74 respondents (51.7%) agree that alternative energy should be considered in GSB design adoption. 65 respondents (45.5%) agree that green roofs should be considered in GSB design adoption. 84 respondents (58.7%) agree that these are energy-efficient materials, and 4 respondents (2.8%) agree that the wall-to-window ratio should be considered in GSB design adoption. 113 respondents (79%) agree that designs for future retrofitting

should be considered in GSB post-construction design. 57 respondents (39.9%) agree that a CO2 sensor monitor should be considered in the GSB post-construction design. 83 respondents (58%) agree that a daylight control mechanism should be considered in the GSB post-construction design, and 67 respondents (46.9%) agree that an energy use data collection system should be considered in the GSB post-construction design. This result shows that GSB adoption in practice is very low.

4.5 Result Summary

The study shows that a higher percentage of the respondents exhibit knowledge of GSB strategies and energy efficiency features. However, there is less participation in GSB, which has a significant impact on architect adoption in practice (48.3%). It further shows that respondents know the environmental, economic, and social benefits of GSB. (54.5%) agree that smart technology helps in green building feature optimization. 58% agree that green products increase energy efficiency in buildings. 3% disagree that GSB can only be used in new buildings, while 60.8% agree that GSB strategies can be used in all building types. All the respondents indicated that GSBs should be adopted in all 4 stages of design. More GSB implementation is needed in Nigeria in earnest.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The architects know the GSB design strategies available due to their educational background and years of work experience. Furthermore, the findings indicate that the level of GSB design strategy adoption in practice is still in its developing phase due to the low participation of Nigerian architects. Although they are aware of the economic, environmental, social, and health benefits of GSB adoption in practice, it is also believed that prioritizing eco-friendly materials such as green products will help the adoption of GSB practices by optimizing energy consumption in high-rise office buildings. Unfortunately, the majority of the features adopted in designs are at the design and approval stages with the building permit authorities. On this note, it is recommended that ARCON should encourage them to incorporate GSB strategies into their construction design and project implementation. ARCON should focus more on training and educating its members on GSB to achieve maximum knowledge and adoption in practice through seminars, training, conferences, etc. on GSB practice. The government should give stakeholders in the construction industry and investors a playing field for more implementation of GSB projects. The developmental policy review will create a more enabling environment for more individuals and corporate developers to invest in the real estate market. In addition, the Edge building certification in Lagos should be a prompt certification process to encourage individuals and investors to participate in registering their building for certification as there are fewer green-certified buildings in Lagos. This study suggests that the Green Building Council of Nigeria (GBCN) be fully set up for increased green building practices that will be used in future projects and in retrofitting existing buildings.

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